

Modelling the decarbonization pathways of Rwanda's power system and ensuring energy security

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Outline

- i. Context
- ii. Scenarios
- iii. Rwanda Reference Energy System
- iv. Results
- v. Conclusions, Policy insights, & Future Work

i. Context

Energy sector status:

- The total installed capacity is **406.4MW**.
- Renewable Energy Share in Power Generation is **48.96%** as of June 2024 with a target to be **70%** by 2030.
- Electricity Demand growth rate exceeded **12%** for the past 3 years, hence increase in electricity imports.

Research Questions:

1. Implications of electricity imports, demand growth and the increasing the renewable energy share on the performance of Rwanda's power system
2. Rwanda's energy mix evolution under decarbonization targets by 2050 to meet the growing electricity demand

Installed Capacity

ii. Scenarios

Using the OSeMOSYS Linear Programming Energy System Model the following scenarios were investigated:

iii. Reference Energy System

iv. Results (1)

1. Imports are predominant in the Business As Usual (BAU) scenario.
2. Scenario 1 introduces solar, coal, natural gas, and nuclear energy to replace the reduced imports.
3. In contrast, Scenario 2 incorporates solar, wind, geothermal, and imports to meet demand with renewable sources.

Results (2)

PRODUCTION BY TECHNOLOGY

1. After capping imports at 150 MW from 2030 onwards, the model prioritizes coal and diesel in the second scenario.
2. The introduction of 70% renewable energy (RE) allows for the reinstatement of imports along with other renewable sources.

Results (3)

Both renewable energy sources (RES) and import reductions scenarios require substantial investments; however, towards the end of the modeling period, investment in renewable energy declines.

In the years 2047–2048, investments for the import reduction scenario remain high compared to the RES scenarios, which are experiencing a slowdown.

Results (4)

The Business As Usual (BAU) scenario emits less CO₂ compared to Scenario 1 due to lower emissions from imports. The Renewable Energy Sources (RES) scenario emits the same level of CO₂ as BAU from 2040 to 2050.

v. Conclusion and Policy Insights

1. Imports are inevitable to meet the demand growth with 26% share at 2050 with RES scenario and hence investment in grid strengthening projects.
2. For energy security purposes, there is need to invest in additional domestic generation that will serve the base load.
3. Exploration of the untapped potential must fast-tracked and executed to meet 70% RE target by 2030.
4. Further research and development is a necessity to the already explored renewable sources i.e solar for cost reduction and storage.

Future Work

Assess the contribution of RE target to the overall NDC target.

THANK YOU